

Farmers' perceptions of rice pest problems and management tactics used in Vietnam

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A May 1992 survey of 685 farmers in the Mekong Delta showed that they perceived the brown planthopper (BPH) to be the most important rice pest problem followed by sheath blight (ShB), rice leaffolders (LF), stem borers (SB), caseworms (CW), rice blast (Bl), leaf yellowing (LY), rice bugs, other defoliators, and thrips.

Farmers reported that pests could be controlled only by pesticides. The main insecticides they used for BPH control were carbamates (58%), although organophosphates, such as methamidophos, methyl parathion, monocrotophos, diazinon, and pyrethroids were also used (see table). For LF control, the main chemicals used were methyl parathion and methamidophos (36%), carbamates (21%), and pyrethroids (20%).

Distribution of first sprays by rice farmers in southern Vietnam.

Rice pests in order of importance and pesticides used on them by farmers in Vietnam, May 1992.

Pesticide	Pests in rank order									
	BPH	ShB	LF	SB	CW	Bl	LY	Defoliators	Bugs	Thrips
<i>Farmers' perception (%) of importance of pests</i>										
	59	12	8	7	4	3	3	3	2	1
<i>Farmers (%) using each pesticide</i>										
Monocrotophos	2	0	9	5	17	0	0	10	13	9
Diazinon	2	0	2	45	2	0	0	5	0	2
Methyl parathion	9	0	21	13	20	0	0	28	17	44
Methamidophos	5	0	16	6	13	0	0	24	13	9
BPMC	40	0	15	6	14	0	0	18	13	15
MIPC	18	0	6	3	5	0	0	5	8	5
Cartap	7	0	10	6	7	0	0	1	4	5
Carbofuran	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Ethofenprox	5	0	3	3	3	0	0	0	0	1
Buprofezin	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cypermethrin	3	0	3	4	12	0	0	4	13	2
Cypermethrin + phosalon	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Deltamethrin	4	0	9	6	4	0	0	4	21	5
Alphamethrin	1	0	4	1	2	0	0	3	0	2
Endosulfan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Di-clorvos	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Benomyl	0	7	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0
Hetacomazole	0	30	0	0	0	14	0	0	0	0
Benomyl + copper sulfate	0	29	0	0	0	38	100	0	0	0
Validamycin	0	33	0	0	0	33	0	0	0	0
Edifenphos	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Farmers considered ShB (*Rhizoctonia solani*) and Bl (*Pyricularia oryzae*) to be the most important disease problems. They used fungicides, such as validamycin and benomyl + copper sulfate, as their main control measures.

Farmers' insecticide use patterns included early season applications of broad-spectrum organophosphates for leaffeeders (see figure). Methyl parathion and methamidophos were the main chemicals used during the seedling and tillering stages. Carbamates, such as BPMC and MIPC, were mainly used during the booting, flowering, and milk grain stages; BPH was the primary target.

The survey showed that broad-spectrum organophosphates are widely

used by farmers in the Mekong Delta. Pest targets were mainly leaffeeders that infest the crop in the early season. These early sprays may not have been necessary because the rice crop can often compensate for early leaf defoliation. Early applications of broad-spectrum insecticides may actually cause ecological disruptions that tend to favor BPH development. Farmers generally believe, however, that the defoliators are important pests and chemical controls are needed.

Farmer participatory research, extension campaigns, and training programs that help farmers realize these early sprays may not be beneficial should be explored further. ■